

**IMKONIYATI CHEKLANGAN BOLALAR MAKTABLARIDA TA'LIM
JARAYONINI TASHKIL ETISH
ORGANIZATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN SCHOOLS FOR
CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES.
ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОГО ПРОЦЕССА В ШКОЛАХ ДЛЯ
ДЕТЕЙ С ОГРАНИЧЕННЫМИ ВОЗМОЖНОСТЯМИ.**

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yo‘nalishi 1-bosqich talabalari:

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar uchun maxsus maktablarda ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etish masalalari yoritilgan. Unda inklyuziv ta'lim tamoyillari, pedagogik yondashuvlar, metodikalar va maxsus sharoitlarni yaratishning ahamiyati muhokama qilinadi. Maqolada turli darajadagi nogironlikka ega bolalarning ta'lim olish huquqini ta'minlash va ularni ijtimoiy integratsiyaga tayyorlashning dolzarb jihatlari o‘rganilgan.

Abstract: This article explores the organization of the educational process in schools for children with disabilities. It discusses the principles of inclusive education, pedagogical approaches, methods, and the importance of creating special conditions. The study addresses the critical aspects of ensuring the right to education for children with various disabilities and preparing them for social integration.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы организации образовательного процесса в школах для детей с ограниченными возможностями. Обсуждаются принципы инклюзивного образования, педагогические подходы, методики и важность создания специальных условий. В статье изучены актуальные аспекты обеспечения права на образование детей с различными формами инвалидности и их подготовки к социальной интеграции.

Kalit so'zlar: Ta'lim jarayoni, Imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar, Inklyuziv ta'lim, Individual yondashuv, Maxsus maktablar, Reabilitatsiya, Pedagogik yondashuvlar, Psixologik yordam, Maxsus dasturlar, Ta'lim texnologiyalari, O'qituvchilar malakasini oshirish, Ijtimoiy integratsiya.

Key words: Educational process, Children with disabilities, Inclusive education, Individual approach, Special schools, Rehabilitation, Pedagogical approaches, Psychological support, Special programs, Educational technologies, Teacher training, Social integration.

Ключевые слова: Процесс, Дети с ограниченными возможностями, Инклюзивное образование, Индивидуальный подход, Специальные школы, Реабилитация, Педагогические подходы, Психологическая поддержка, Специальные программы, Образовательные технологии, Подготовка учителей, Социальная интеграция.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY Currently, in Uzbekistan, along with many other countries, opportunities are being created for children with disabilities to receive education and training, to receive medical treatment, and the rights of such people and children are strengthened and protected by legislation. The international standards of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, as well as the Law "On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities", which provides for the use of the term "person with disabilities" instead of the word "disabled" in our country serves to express the rights and interests of persons belonging to the above category [2]. This year, within the framework of the program "Development of education for hearing-impaired children" of the "Zamin" foundation, the "Zamin Education" project was launched at the specialized ICT-school named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi. support, prepare them to enter higher educational institutions, as well as improve the qualifications of teachers of specialized boarding schools in the field of information technologies and develop a new methodology consists of output. This project is being implemented in cooperation with the specialized ICT school named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi, where the first educational resource center "Zamin Education" was opened. In the classroom designed for the project, auxiliary equipment aimed at improving the quality of data reception - FM-system is installed. Also, each student is provided with individual hearing aids. The chairman of the board of trustees of the "Zamin" foundation, Ziroat Mirziyoyeva, visited this class to get acquainted with the educational process, and talked with the students of the upper classes of the specialized boarding schools No. 102 and 106, the children shared their impressions and spoke about the topics under study. After the successful results of the first educational resource center, it is planned to organize "Zamin Education" classes in all regions of the country.

We will consider more in-depth information on the topic of organizing the educational process for children with disabilities in the following areas: Categories of children with disabilities Children with physical disabilities: limitations in movement or physical activity (for example, cerebral palsy). Children with sensory disabilities: visually impaired (blind or visually impaired) or hearing impaired. Children with intellectual disabilities: retardation of intellectual development or other disabilities⁸¹. Children living with emotional and social problems: disorders on the autism

⁸¹ Yevdokimova I.V. 'Maxsus pedagogika nazariyasi va amaliyoti'.

spectrum, attention deficit syndrome (ADHD), etc. The main directions of the pedagogical system Special educational institutions: Schools and centers specially adapted for children with disabilities. Adaptive Education Programs: Programs designed for special needs based on state curricula. Multidisciplinary approach: Educators, defectologists, speech therapists, psychologists and medical specialists work together. Basic principles of organizing the educational process. Inclusion: Integration of children with special needs into the general school community. Individuality: Developing an educational approach that fits the needs and capabilities of each child. Continuous monitoring: Regular monitoring of the child's development and revision of the curriculum accordingly. Supportive environment: Ensuring children feel safe and valued. Methods and technologies used in the educational process Didactic materials: Braille books, hearing aids, enlarged texts for ease of viewing. Information technology: Special computer programs and devices (eg voice assistants). Play activities: Learning through play with children is especially important in psychological and social development. Creative activity: Developing children's skills through drawing, playing music, manual labor. Qualification and training of teachers Pedagogues and defectologists must undergo special training and courses. Ability to work in a multidisciplinary team. Gaining knowledge of psychological support and stress management. 6. Cooperation with parents Special training and advice for parents. Methodical guides for working with children at home. Periodic reports and communication on child development. Literature I recommend using the following resources: Bogdashina O.S., "Autism and pedagogy: a practical guide.". Bim-Bad B.M., "Fundamentals of defectology." Yevdokimova I.V., "Theory and practice of special pedagogy.". Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan: Law "On the rights of persons with disabilities". UNESCO and UNICEF reports: international recommendations on inclusive education and support for children with disabilities.

In Uzbekistan, the issue of education for visually impaired children has been established in cooperation with the state and international organizations. Below is information about important measures and programs in this area:

Special schools and equipment Special schools for visually impaired children are being equipped with modern technologies and materials. For example, textbooks, relief maps and other special educational tools are provided based on the Braille alphabet

Development of inclusive education On the basis of the "Provisional Regulation on Inclusive Education for Children and Adolescents with Disabilities" adopted in 2005, efforts are being made to include blind and visually impaired children in the general education system. In this system, in addition to state education standards, correctional programs are used and specially equipped rooms are organized.

Rehabilitation and support services The Ministry of Public Education plans to establish rehabilitation centers and special courses for blind children. International experience and local conditions are taken into account.⁸²

Attracting young people to education Youth leaders in the neighborhoods are taking measures to involve blind and visually impaired children in education. In this process, opportunities for children's education at home are also being created. These efforts expand the educational opportunities of children with disabilities and help them successfully integrate into society.

A number of programs and initiatives are being implemented in Uzbekistan for the education of hearing-impaired children. In this direction, the main focus is on attracting modern technologies and creating a special environment:

Application of innovative technologies: In special education, e-learning programs and mobile applications adapted to the needs of hearing-impaired children are being developed. This not only makes the work of deaf pedagogues easier, but also makes it easier for parents to deal with their children.⁸³

Schools and infrastructure: Although special conditions are created for children with disabilities in some schools, a fully inclusive environment is not established in general educational institutions. Due to the lack of specialized schools, many children are forced to receive education at home. This limits the opportunity to get quality education

Pedagogical approach: Special methods are being developed for teachers. Through the use of information and communication technologies, the possibilities of individual work with children, effective evaluation and development of their educational results are increasing.

These initiatives serve to realize children's intellectual potential and create equal opportunities in education. At the same time, improvement of the inclusive education system is recognized as one of the urgent tasks.

Organization of the educational process in schools for children with disabilities is a very important and complex task. These schools require not only special educational methods, but also an individual approach. The educational process should serve not only to increase academic knowledge, but also to social, emotional and physical development of children. Special methods and training programs Educational programs for children with disabilities are different from traditional programs. They are modified according to the needs of the children, for example, they can be supported through polite teaching, visual materials, teaching aids and technology (ie, interactive displays, voice assistants and other tools). An individual plan is developed to adapt the students to the lessons. Training of teachers and special

⁸² O'zbekiston Respublikasi qonunchiligi: nogironligi bo'lgan shaxslarning huquqlari to'g'risida'gi qonun.

⁸³ ResearchGate saytidagi maqolada O'zbekistondagi eshitish qobiliyati zaif va jismoniy nuqsonli bolalar uchun ta'lim tizimining hozirgi holati, jumladan, maxsus maktablar, infratuzilma va pedagogic yondashuvlar haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

specialists Teachers must undergo special training to work with children with disabilities. In working with such children, it is necessary to cooperate with psychologists, speech therapists, defectologists and other specialists. Teachers should also know how to use an individual approach with children and teach each child according to his needs. Organization of the classroom environment For children with disabilities, it is necessary for the classroom environment to be comfortable and safe. This means not only providing physical freedom, but also the availability of technologies adapted to the learning process, special learning materials and a space modified for physical conditions. Focus on cognitive and social development Children with disabilities need not only to learn, but also to develop social skills. In the educational process, it is necessary to attach great importance to the development of social skills such as teamwork, communication, maintaining emotional stability. Frequent evaluation and analysis Monitoring the effectiveness of the educational process.

Goals and tasks of inclusive education The goal of inclusive education is to create an unobstructed and adapted educational environment for students with special educational needs by using special tools and methods at school with the involvement of special pedagogues, their effective adaptation to society and full development. is to provide high-quality general secondary education that serves the harmonization. Schools provide comprehensive support to children with special educational needs and their parents in receiving corrective pedagogical support and career guidance. The tasks of inclusive education are as follows: creating a single adapted social environment for students with different development opportunities, which excludes any disadvantage and ensures equal treatment of all children; forming a tolerant attitude towards the problems of students with special educational needs in the public and all participants of the educational process; development of mental and social potential of children with special educational needs along with healthy children in the educational process; creating an opportunity for all students to master general secondary education programs in accordance with state educational standards; all-round development of students, emotional-volitional sphere, activation of knowledge activities, formation of social skills and qualities; by giving advice to families raising children with special educational needs, raising the awareness of parents in the field of education and upbringing of their children, pedagogical approach, the use of educational methods and tools, providing them with psychological and pedagogical support support.

Problems of inclusive education. In many countries, the introduction of inclusive education is not recorded in the state normative documents; Negative attitude towards disabled children; The problem of invisibility of children with disabilities in society; The problem of children with disabilities not being seen at school; Financial problems; Adaptation of educational institutions; Large number of students in the class; Poverty; Discrimination based on gender differences; Dependence of children

with disabilities on others; Emergency situations, conflicts, refugees; Personnel issues. A legitimate question arises, why should children with disabilities be included in the inclusive education system? What is the need to move to an inclusive education system by solving the arguments presented above? Indeed, it is not easy to solve the problems facing the education system. But there are many benefits of this education system, including:

- Inclusive education helps to break the cycle of poverty; S Inclusive education improves the quality of education for all; C Prevents discrimination; S Inclusive education leads to more inclusiveness. Principles of inclusive education:

- The value of a person does not depend on his abilities and achievements.
- Everyone has the ability to think and feel.
- Everyone has the ability to hear and communicate.
- Everyone needs each other.
- Full and real education of the person is realized only in real cooperation.
- All people need support from their peers.
- What makes all learners successful is not their inability to do something, but their ability to do something.

- Collaboration enhances human life in every way. Educational institutions under the inclusive education system include; pre-school education, upper secondary education, secondary special vocational and higher education. The goal of these educational institutions is to create an open learning environment by removing barriers between children's education and career preparation. There will be no opportunity to use separate programs and textbooks in comprehensive schools. The inclusive education system differs from the integrated education system by its content - essence, purpose, tasks and program of action.

Proper acquisition of speech at the right time allows the child to interact freely with the people around him, helps to control his behavior, helps the child to develop his mental activity, and finally, the process of education at school relieves. Children with disabilities enter language later than their healthy peers, the first word is delayed until the child is three, and sometimes five years old. First of all, it is necessary to note the pronunciation defect here. 90% of mentally retarded children in the 1st grade have speech defects. Most children have phonemic hearing impairment, speech organs and their movement defects. There are serious difficulties in acquiring vocabulary. Impressive speech lags far behind the development of expressive speech. They do not understand many words that express generalizing concepts of an abstract nature, they have difficulty understanding the concepts used in a figurative sense, they perceive them precisely. Students with disabilities also have difficulty in constructing sentences. Sentences are simple, short, and there are many mistakes in the mutual adaptation of words, sentences with complex connections are rarely used. Mentally retarded students find it difficult to compare one thing to another, to reveal the causal connections of events, moreover, the lack of sufficient and clear

understanding of the events causes the thinking of mentally retarded students to remain completely unclear and incomplete.

Not understanding the meaning of the sentence is one of the characteristics of the speech of students with disabilities [6]. The fact that children do not fully understand what they read, hear and see leads to a number of mistakes in their speech. All speech defects of children with disabilities cause difficulties in the process of teaching them, they do not always understand the teacher's explanations, they do not understand the teacher's explanations correctly. But the experiences of advanced teachers-defectologists have shown that with the help of a specially organized process of education, it is possible to correct the speech activity of students with mental retardation, that is, to improve their role in the development of the general personality. The first 2 weeks of the academic year are focused on identifying and checking the speech of new students. In this case, the speech therapist examines the student's oral and written speech in 2 stages: At the 1st stage, the speech of students in the class is checked in general condition and children with speech defects are identified among the students. In the 3rd stage, the student with a speech disorder is identified and diagnosed individually in the conditions of the speech therapy room. The plan of individual training is mainly reflected in the speech card of the speech pathologist. Organization of logopedic examination of the speech process Examination of the speech of first-grade students with disabilities begins with the study of the student during the lesson. Such a frontal (gross) examination not only saves time for the speech therapist, but it allows to observe the natural state of the students' speech activity, clearly expresses the students' response and the state of oral speech. At the same time, the speech therapist will have the opportunity to get acquainted with the personal characteristics of the students: work skills, attention, memory, intellectual level. Frontal inspection can be carried out in different ways, as well as in an integrated way. In this case, the speech therapist observes the students' answers in the teacher's office, and then, in turn, the speech therapist conducts a question-and-answer session based on a meaningful picture recommended by him, asks him to make up a story and speak. It should also be taken into account that the speech examination process should have an educational nature.

A child's lagging behind in education and training is the result of not mastering mental functions. For example, a child's discontinuity in putting on clothes is not due to a weak memory, but because he has not acquired the necessary skills to carry out this process. Along with the methods of psychoreaction of such a mental problem, the child can be presented with pictures showing how to put on clothes in the correct sequence. L.S. Vygotsky puts forward the idea that the health of the social environment is of primary importance for children with limited health opportunities. He also likens the development of children with disabilities to a plant with bad roots. "Its thin roots do not adapt to the layers and shape of the nutrient soil. They cannot reach the nutritious layers of the soil, and get into the dry and toxic layer. Such a

plant could bloom under suitable conditions, but under normal conditions, it did not reach the peak of development and withered.⁸⁴ Therefore, it is appropriate to develop the educational system taking into account the specific aspects of each nation and people, national traditions, customs, goals and tasks of the state, and the mental and physical development of the students. In the case of children with disabilities, if adults help the child's wishes and aspirations as much as possible without opposing the child's will and independence, the difficulties in the process of forming his personality will disappear by themselves. Stubbornness, obstinacy, and disobedience appear in a child with limited abilities as a result of excessive manipulation by adults. Psychologist L.M. Krijanovskaya has widely explained the ways of educating children with disabilities through the methods of psychological correction in the inclusive education system. In his opinion, the cooperation of school psychologist, pedagogue, educator and parents should be inextricably linked in order to be effective in the inclusive education system and to achieve good results.

Currently, the Ministry of Construction, in cooperation with interested ministries, is developing requirements for the buildings and equipment of educational institutions in order to create a barrier-free environment and opportunities for children with special educational needs. According to it, general education schools where inclusive education is set to be introduced as a test will be equipped according to the needs of children involved in inclusive education. Creating sufficient conditions for students with special educational needs to receive quality education is reflected in the requirements for modern schools and the methodology and procedure for evaluating general secondary educational institutions based on them.

In the 2021-2022 school year, it is planned to cover 24% of children with special educational needs with inclusive education. By 2025, this indicator is expected to reach 40 percent. It is also decided to open basic correctional classes for children with special educational needs in one general education school located in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent city. Children diagnosed with attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), dyslexia, and autism are admitted to such classes.

Amendments have been made to the curricula of centers for retraining and professional development of pedagogic staff on the implementation of inclusive practice in the educational system, providing for special training sessions related to education. In addition, psychologists of general education schools are conducting trainings against all kinds of violence, oppression and discrimination among students and teachers.⁸⁵

SUMMARY

If you look at the plans, everything is beautiful: if the goals until 2025 are implemented as in the concept, children with disabilities should be educated in the

⁸⁴ Bogdashina O. S. "Autizm va pedagogika" amaliy qo'llanma.

⁸⁵ Bim-Bad B.M. "Defektologiya asoslari"

same conditions as others, they should not lack textbooks and study guides. Such children, like healthy children, can go to school without difficulty and find their way in the future more easily. Society does not look at people with disabilities as strangers. Only the full implementation of the concept should be strictly controlled, nothing should be left on paper, and the Ministry of Public Education should pay attention to the concerns of teachers of specialized schools and listen to them. it is appropriate to study their thoughts as well.

References:

1. Bogdashina O.S "Autism and pedagogy" practical manual
2. Bim-Bad B. M. "Fundamentals of defectology"
3. Yevdokimova I.V. "Theory and practice of special pedagogy"
4. Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan: Law "On the rights of persons with disabilities"
5. The ResearchGate article provides detailed information on the current state of the education system for children with hearing and physical disabilities in Uzbekistan, including special schools, infrastructure, and pedagogical approaches.
6. A study published in the journal Science and Education highlighted the shortcomings of the education system for children with disabilities, including the lack of inclusive conditions in general schools and the limitations of special schools.